

On the Semantic Analysis of Open (Government) Data Portals' Metadata Provision and Schema

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Abstract

The ever-increasing amount of data available through Open Data portals follows the momentum and proliferation of Open Data initiatives and, apart from the numerous benefits offered, poses a reality which brings forth several challenges. Metadata quality and management are key aspects in this regard; in their absence affecting the interoperability, findability, and consequently, open data consumption. The present study aims to analyse several semantic aspects of 3 major international data portals and their metadata schemas mapped to the main DCAT schema classes in order to assess the current status regarding metadata provision and aiming towards prospective standardisation and improved semantic interoperability of the datasets available. The analysis revealed several persisting challenges, including the lack of standardised information (e.g., controlled vocabularies) as accepted values of the identified mandatory metadata fields in use, or, in the case of existing standardisation schemas, a misalignment and lack of consensus among the different portals. The study also pinpoints future research lines centred around the elicitation of guidelines and practices to standardise not only descriptive but also domain-specific metadata provision across the portals, facilitating the process towards the identification of minimum sets of metadata descriptions applicable to various contexts, and reaching one step closer to the envisioned interoperable ODPs paradigm.

CCS Concepts

• semantic interoperability; • controlled vocabularies; • metadata schema; • open data portal; • open data;

ACM Reference Format:

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1 INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing amount of data available through Open Data portals at a national or international level follows the momentum and proliferation of Open Data initiatives and, apart from the numerous benefits offered by this valuable resource, poses a reality which brings forth several challenges. Metadata quality and management are key aspects in this regard; in their absence affecting the findability, interoperability, accessibility, and consequently, open data consumption. While various technological improvements have been introduced during the last decade, the harmonisation of data sources available remains a topic still unsaturated, requiring further research, in order to catch up with the heterogeneous nature of the different environments involved in open data provision.

Metadata can be descriptive (e.g., containing information to facilitate resource discovery), structural (e.g., data models), or administrative (e.g., providing information for resource management) and the importance of metadata management has long been established as the means to aim towards improved data availability, quality, persistence over time, and proper, open licensing (joinup.eu, 2014) [1]. Adding to the previously mentioned properties, and in direct alignment with data quality, semantic interoperability also holds a prominent position, especially as far as descriptive and structural metadata is concerned. Vocabulary reuse at the service of metadata provision or enrichment targets standardisation and interoperability by deploying existing specifications and already established (core) schemas, such as the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT), avoiding a custom metadata schema. For instance, the DCAT application profile (DCAT-AP) for data portals in Europe reuses terms from known, existing vocabularies such as Dublic Core, the Simple Knowledge Organization System (skos), the Friend of a Friend vocabulary (foaf), and more, allowing for the reusability of already specified terms, combined with the help of RDF schema [1]. Ideally, descriptive metadata does not leave room for assigning free-text descriptions but follows standardised approaches, such as controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, or other predefined lists of values (e.g., ISO) that metadata can be expressed as, allowing for an automatic and seamless exchange of information among heterogeneous systems, also known as metadata homegenisation. DCAT-AP is a strong candidate to undertake this role and facilitate metadata exchange, considering its wide use across several data portals, and its compliance with other known and accepted schemas. At the same time, metadata can be domain independent (generic, domain-agnostic metadata) or domain dependent (domain-specific), the former describing general aspects of given data objects and the latter describing data of specific knowledge domains in which the data object conceptually belongs. In this study, the main focus is the first type, where standardisation is enclosed by tighter margins and less

room for flexibility regarding the data schema. Several methods can be used to harmonise data standards among various data sources [2], more specifically, Zeng and Chan (2006) [3] suggest derivation (in other words the inheritance of a schema created by another one and maintaining similar elements), switching-across (a switching mechanism among several schemas), the use of application profiles (ensuring similar structure and elements), crosswalks (or mapping of elements among data standards), metadata frameworks (for standardisation in a given knowledge field), or metadata registries (a collection of metadata schemas). In the context of this study, crosswalks are an aspect to consider in the examination of the chosen Open Data portals, attempting to discover common ground among the existing practices for (meta)data provision. Moreover, DCAT satisfies various of the approaches suggested by Zeng and Chan (2006) [3] and it is thus included as a research parameter for the purpose of this study.

All things considered, the present work aims to analyse semantic aspects of 3 major international open data portals to assess their current state regarding metadata schemas and prospective standardisation aiming towards improved semantic interoperability of the datasets available (focusing on descriptive and administrative metadata). In this vein, the main research question of the study is: “can one search query run across the given open data portals (ODPs) and deliver all the relevant results? In other words, can a semantically interoperable query be designed to return all the related data from all the other ODPs?”. To address this question, the present study includes an analysis framework of several aspects of semantic value regarding the studied ODPs, as well as potential mappings of currently used schemas to the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) metadata schema, ensuring compliance to standardised metadata representation. This paper is structured as follows: the Background Section refers to underlying research on metadata quality assessment but also evaluation of ODPs and linked open data sources for datasets and draws the connections and intuition behind the present study. In the Methodology Section, the analysis framework for the ODPs is introduced, while the results and initial conclusions of this small-scale study are presented in Section 4. Finally, the last Sections include the elaboration on the insights received, as well as the considered limitations and suggested future directions of this study.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Metadata Quality Assessment of Open Data Portals

Metadata quality evaluation and assessment studies for Open (Government) Data portals have been ongoing, examining the (meta)data model adoption of the portals, the quality of the available datasets, and other points of reference related to either technical or user-centred parameters. The evaluation frameworks vary; Xiao et al. (2018) [4] studied the current usage of open data platforms and metadata adoption of several local (city level) OGD portals in the United States based on the National Information Standards Organization (NISO) standard to assess their metadata functionality, this standard referring to six metadata attributes: discovery, display, interoperability, digital-object management, preservation, and navigation (Riley, 2017) [5]. The results of Xiao et al. (2018) [4]

show that Socrata and ArcGIS Open Data are the predominantly adopted platforms, followed by CKAN but at a much lower percentage, while, regarding the metadata schema, many platforms have designed their own custom schema and others decided to follow standard ones, such as RDF the way it is presented in Dublin Core and DCAT. The research by Xiao et al. (2018) [4] benchmarked the results against NISO, and, as far as the attribute of interoperability is concerned (which is the main focus of the present study), several drawbacks and inconsistencies among the platforms were identified; the effective data exchange between system is hindered by the fact that only CKAN supports the element of “format” (technical and preservation metadata are important for seamless exchange), while Socrata and ArcGIS do not. Similarly, “file size” is only included in the schema of ArcGIS, while the same does not apply for the license or rights field, present in the other two platforms. In general, metadata variance, such as schema customisation hampers interoperability and cross-platform data discovery, and proper documentation describing the adopted schema for each portal is required to help users understand the data available [4]. Overall, the quality of metadata was proven better in CKAN (more widely used in Europe and Central Asia) than the other two most predominantly used in North America, an indication of why metadata quality ranks lower there than in other countries [4].

Umbrich et al. (2015) [6] developed an ODP monitoring and assessment framework and identified strong heterogeneity in metadata keys, values and tags across portals, while the successive research by Neumaier et al. (2016) [7] defined several ODP quality metrics to be evaluated automatically and efficiently. To alleviate heterogeneity among different adopted schemas by common data platforms, Neumaier et al. (2016) [7] performed a mapping between different metadata keys of three platforms (Socrata, CKAN, and OpenDataSoft) and DCAT (with its four main classes: `dcat:Catalog`, `dcat:CatalogRecord`, `dcat:Dataset`, and `dcat:Distribution`), grouping the quality metrics of the DCAT specification in five dimensions: Existence, Conformance, Retrievability, Accuracy, and Open Data, against which the corresponding metadata keys were compared and mapped. This homogenisation approach resulted in a few conclusions, among others, such as that several DCAT properties cannot be automatically mapped to the examined metadata models, that a big proportion of the datasets do not provide machine-readable information, and the existence of metadata properties that are highly portal dependent in the form of extra keys, which aim to cover up for missing DCAT properties (e.g., spatial or temporal context) but lack homogeneity and agreement among them.

Nogueras-Iso et al. (2021) [8] focused on DCAT-compliant metadata models and proposed an extended method to evaluate the Open Data catalog of the Spanish Government taking into consideration current approaches towards metadata quality assessment, such as the ISO 19157 method. As mentioned earlier, the vocabularies based on DCAT are mainly focused on the three main classes: Catalogs, Datasets and Distributions, however, for the sake of simplicity, Nogueras-Iso et al. (2021) [8] used the Spanish proposal for DCAT-based metadata, also known as NTI (Norma Técnica de Interoperabilidad de Reutilización de Recursos de Información) which contains representative properties of the Dataset and Distribution entities. The research resulted in a new evaluation method based on ISO 19157 (which includes several and versatile quality

elements) and the analysis of the NTI metadata model, one of the most critical points being that this methodology is extensible and applicable to more DCAT-based vocabulary or schema, allowing for the improvement of metadata compliance and interoperability.

2.2 Evaluation of Open Data Portals

Apart from the evaluation of adopted metadata schemas of ODPs and focusing on the evaluation of Open Data portals per se, Herrera-Melo and González-Sanabria (2020) [9] proposed an evaluation methodology for ODPs in Spain, Brazil, Costa Rica, Taiwan and the European Union based on existing, applied methods and standards which target different aspects of ODPs, such as the Five stars Berners-Lee's model for openness and usability, Meloda for data reuse, the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) for metadata evaluation, and others. The proposed methodology by Herrera-Melo and González-Sanabria (2020) [9] consists of two approaches: the datasets, and the portal itself, the former including the dimensions of quality, use, and metadata, and the latter including the structure, usability, and communication. The first approach of this evaluation method by Herrera-Melo and González-Sanabria (2020) [9], which focuses on datasets and includes the dimension of metadata (use, completeness, and recoverability) is the one also considered in the present study. Various characteristics (functional, semantic and technological) of OGD sources in Greece were analysed by Loukis et al. (2013) [10] of which the semantic analysis perspective included the 5-stars Berners-Lee model for open data rating, the 5-stars Maturity Scheme of Metadata Management (ISA) (the highest 5-star rank here being Linked Open Metadata, and the 4-star rank being Open Reusable Metadata), RDF-compliance, and data licensing. The majority of the examined OGD sources in Greece reached only the lowest level of the 5-star Berners-Lee model, followed by a much smaller percentage of 2 stars, and very few of them managed to score higher levels. The ISA scheme in this case was similar; the majority of the sources were at the first stage of "metadata ignorance", a much smaller percentage reached a higher metadata maturity level, and only 2% reached the highest level of the scale. In addition to these, the problematic aspect of custom metadata schemas in the OGD sources was also present [10]. Similarly, Oliveira et al. (2016) [11] analysed OGD portals in Brazil, including evaluation criteria such as data integration and management, schema quality issues, and datasets heterogeneity, identifying several open issues and challenges such as the lack of proper metadata of datasets; even if CKAN- the predominantly used platform in Brazil- specifies a set of core attributes, most portals do not use standardised values for them, the low re-use of existing vocabularies and ontologies, and the low provision of human-readable metadata for dataset description and structure.

2.3 Linked Open Data Sources for Datasets

The highest rank (5-star) of the Maturity Scheme of Metadata Management (ISA) [15] is the Linked Open Metadata and linked open data sources for various thematic disciplines have been under development to provide efficient data modeling and the provision of interlinked knowledge graphs. Färber and Lamprecht (2022) [12] demonstrated an approach to construct RDF knowledge graphs and created the academic landscape DSKG (dataset knowledge graph),

which establishes links between datasets, publications, and authors, while resolving name disambiguations and other semantic inconsistencies. DSKG is integrated into the Linked Open Data Cloud (LODC) and its metadata properties were mapped to the DCAT RDF vocabulary to ensure compliance with all DCAT-based schemas [12]. In a similar way, Wu et al. (2021) [13] proposed an open data portal to host a climate domain knowledge graph created for Ireland and England's National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) daily data with linked data as the underlying approach. The proliferation of open data portal platforms which foster dataset interlinking was also studied by Figueiredo et al. (2021) [14] who designed LigADOS, an approach to establish connections between datasets which share proximal content. Figueiredo et al. (2021) [14] emphasised the important contribution of specialised vocabularies (e.g., DCAT, VoID, Schema.org) to portals for richer descriptive metadata annotation. It is additionally noted that specialised vocabularies are not capable of providing content-related interlinkage due to their simple metadata tag assignment, the utilisation of domain specific vocabularies can be beneficial to undertake this role, and when combined with the former, they allow for more sophisticated metadata descriptions and the establishment of semantic links among datasets.

3 METHODOLOGY

Although current metadata schemas of portals aim for compliance to known, standardised ones (e.g., DCAT), as presented in the previous Section, research shows that there is still a variety of recurrent issues to be tackled [4] and plenty of room for improvement with respect to semantically interoperable information available. The main goal of this study is, by taking into account the existing literature and research on the subject, to analyse the current status in metadata schemas of major open (government) data portals and identify aspects which potentially hinder semantic interoperability. For the purpose of this study, 3 of the currently biggest open data portals have been selected for analysis: the European Data Portal, the national open data portal of the United States and the national open data portal of Canada. The overall method for this study is based on a qualitative research methodology approach.

The criteria of selection for the above-mentioned portals include the amount of data available through them, whether the open data portal receives government support by the respective governmental bodies that are responsible for the publishing and dataset caretaking, popularity within the open data community, accessibility (portal functionalities, language of navigation, APIs, etc.), and level of impact (e.g., if the data available on the portal is being used for research purposes, business, policymaking, and more). Further parameters which were considered include the geographic coverage of the datasets available, the presence of metadata, the perceived quality of the datasets, and user engagement features of the portal which allow for interaction and possibly more advanced functionalities (e.g., visualisation) on the offered data. The selected open data portals receive support from their respective government(s), offering access to data coming from public agencies, ministries, statistical bureaus, etc., while most of the open data portals are actively engaged in open data communities and social innovation initiatives.

Figure 1: The overall methodological approach for the ODP metadata schema analysis

As mentioned previously, the main goal is to assess the ODPs current state regarding metadata schemas to aim towards improved prospective standardisation and answer the question of whether, in the current situation and a hypothetical scenario, it would be possible to run a semantically interoperable query which would successfully retrieve all the relevant results from all the examined ODPs. Within the context of this study, the semantic analysis includes the following aspects:

- identifying the adopted metadata schema (or schemas) used by the ODPs
- examining whether the ODPs use the same dataset categorisation for each sector (same category themes)
- examining whether the ODPs make use of standardised metadata terms (e.g., controlled vocabularies)
- identifying the mandatory metadata fields for each ODP
- identifying the metadata fields for which the use of controlled vocabularies is optional (recommended)
- identifying the metadata fields for which the use of controlled vocabularies is mandatory
- identifying the minimum set of metadata fields required for each ODP
- identifying the minimum set of metadata fields required for all simultaneously (fulfilling the mandatory demands of all the ODPs)
- identifying the minimum set of metadata fields which are currently connected (currently fully aligned among the ODPs).

In addition to the above-mentioned parameters, a mapping comparison between the DCAT main classes (in this context the focus is on `dcat:Dataset` and `dcat:Distribution` classes) and classes of the adopted metadata schema was performed. The rationale behind this is an adaptation of the DCAT mapping of metadata keys analysis by Neumaier et al. (2016) [7] in the context of this study. Finally, after the analysis, the Metadata Management Maturity model (ISA) [15] is taken into account to assess the current level of metadata management quality in the portals. Other approaches include the benchmarking of analysis results to known evaluation standards, such as the ones proposed in [4] and [8], including the National Information Standards Organization (NISO) standard and ISO 19157 respectively. It is worth mentioning that for the purpose of this study only descriptive and administrative metadata are considered.

The overall methodological approach and analysis framework parameters considered are presented in Figure 1.

Considering the above-mentioned parameters chosen for the ODP metadata analysis in this study, the main findings and explanation are presented in the following Section.

4 RESULTS

The cross-tabulation between the open data platforms and metadata schemas used is quite high among the included ODPs, and CKAN is the main platform in use. The EU open data portal harvests many different metadata standards and transforms them into the standard DCAT-AP schema, while it also supports GeoDCAT-AP and StatDCAT-AP for more details on the respective domains. The internal metadata interface and API of the EU data portal are standard DCAT-AP forms as well. The Canadian open data portal uses their own Government of Canada Foundational Metadata Schema (or GC Meta), and the US open data portal has DCAT-US Schema v1.1 (Project Open Data Metadata Schema) as the main schema to describe its metadata. The results of the analysis framework described in the Method Section are shown in Table 1.

To begin with, the three open data portals are using different thematic organisation for their available datasets and sectoral data tag assignment. The EU data portal currently uses 14 thematic categories, the Canadian data portal uses 19 thematic subjects, and the US data portal follows a slightly different approach of categorisation (as listed in Table 1). While some concepts are certainly related, identical, or of higher or lower conceptual hierarchical order, the general adoption of themes differs a lot among the three portals. The number of mandatory metadata fields varies across the ODPs; the EU one requiring 11 metadata fields, the Canadian portal requiring 19, and the US portal 12. The notion of controlled vocabularies use is shown in the line “Standardised Terms/ Use of Controlled Vocabularies” of Table 1 and presents the identified metadata fields of the three portals which currently use or highly recommend the use of standardised terms or controlled vocabularies (codelists). Although controlled vocabulary use is highly recommended in the metadata schemas, many of them are not mandatory to follow and can still be replaced by free text or custom input. This aspect was identified through the mapping between the DCAT main classes and the respective classes (and values) of the analysed ODPs (Table 2), where it becomes easier to compare the current differences and

Table 1: The analysed metadata-related aspects of the ODPs

Semantic Aspect /ODPs	European Open Data Portal	Canadian Open Data Portal	US Open Data Portal
Sector Categorisation (Thematic Categories)	14 Categories: Economy and Finance, Education, Culture and Sport, Energy, Environment, Government and Public Sector, Health, Agriculture, Fisheries, Forestry and Food, Transport, Science and Technology, Regions and Cities, Population and Society, Justice, Legal System and Public Safety, International Issues, Provisional data	Filters-> Subject (19 subjects): Nature and Environment, Form Descriptors, Science and Technology, Economics and Industry, Government and Politics, Health and Safety, Society and Culture, Persons, Transport, Labour, Agriculture, Law, Information and Communications, Education and Training, Language and Linguistics, Processes, Arts Music Literature, Military, History and Archaeology	Topics: Local Government, Climate, Older Adults Health Data Collection, Energy Topic Categories: around 49 sub-categories generalising or specialising the Topics.
Mandatory Metadata Fields	11	19	12
Standardised Terms/ Use of Controlled Vocabularies	Some fields make use of certain defined values- although there are still some that do not. Fields identified that make use of controlled vocabs (recommended or mandatory): “dct:issued”, “dct:modified”, “dct:identifier”, “dct:language”, “dct:accrualPeriodicity”, “dct:theme”, “dct:license”, “dct:format”, “dct:mediaType”.	Almost all examined fields have the option of usage of certain defined values. Fields identified that make use of controlled vocabs (recommended or mandatory): “description”, “issued”, “modified”, “identifier”, “keyword”, “language”, “publisher”, “contactPoint”, “accrualPeriodicity”, “landingPage”, “theme”, “license”, “downloadURL”, “format”, “mediaType”, “byteSize”.	Some fields make use of certain defined values- although most fields have freely accepted ones. Fields identified that make use of controlled vocabs (recommended or mandatory): “issued”, “modified”, “language”, “accrualPeriodicity”, “theme”, “mediaType”.
Recommended use of controlled vocabularies	dct:identifier, dct:language, dcat:contactPoint, dct: license, dct:format, dct:publisher	“metadataRecordIdentifier”(dct:identifier), “descriptiveKeywords” (dcat:keyword), “pointOfContact”(dcat:contactPoint), “extent” (dct:byteSize), “resourceURL” (dcat:downloadURL)	“theme”, “identifier”
Mandatory use of controlled vocabularies	dct:issued, dct:modified, dct:accrualPeriodicity, dcat:landingPage, dct:theme, dct:mediaType	“dateReleased”, “date_modified”, “language”, “publisherCurrentOrganizationName”, “maintenanceAndUpdateFrequency”, “homepageURLEnglish”, “topic_category”, “format”, “resourceType”	“mediaType”, “downloadURL”, “license”, “modified”, “issued”, “accrualPeriodicity”, “contactPoint”, “language”
Minimum set of metadata fields required for each ODP	dct:title, dct:issued, dct:modified, dct:identifier, dct:language, dct:publisher, dcat:landingPage, dct:format, dct:mediaType	“resourceTitleFrench”, Term Name: “description”, “dateReleased”, “date_modified”, “metadataRecordIdentifier”, “descriptiveKeywords”, “language”, “publisherCurrentOrganizationName”, “pointOfContact”, “maintenanceAndUpdateFrequency”, “topic_category”, “license”, “resourceURL”, “format”, “resourceType”, “extent”	“title”, “description”, “modified”, “identifier”, “keyword”, “publisher”, “contactPoint”, “license”, “downloadURL”, “mediaType”

Minimum set of metadata fields required for all ODPs (17)	Original metadata term names: dct:title, “description”, “dateReleased”, dct:modified, “descriptiveKeywords”, “identifier”, “contactPoint”, “license”, dct:language, dct:publisher, “maintenanceAndUpdateFrequency”, dcat:landingPage, “topic_category”, “downloadURL”, “format”, “resourceType”, “extent”	DCAT equivalents: dct:title, dct:description, dct:issued, dct:modified, dct:identifier, dcat:keyword, dct:language, dct:publisher, dcat:contactPoint, dct:accrualPeriodicity, dcat:landingPage, dcat:theme, dct:license, dcat:downloadURL, dct:format, dct:mediaType, dct:byteSize	
Minimum set of metadata fields connected (currently fully interoperable)	dct:issued-“dateReleased”-“issued” dct:modified-“modified”-“modified” dct:language-“language”-No dcat:contactPoint-No-“contactPoint” dct:mediaType-No-“mediaType”		
Metadata Management Maturity Model (ISA) level	Level 5: Linked Open Metadata	Level 5: Linked Open Metadata	Level 5: Linked Open Metadata

similarities in the adoption of controlled vocabulary use. In an exhaustive approach, all the controlled vocabularies currently in use by the European data portal are available through the EU’s EU vocabulary list (specifically under Authority Tables and Code lists), while the full list of controlled vocabularies in use by the Canadian open data portal can be found in the Canadian Government’s GC Enterprise Data Reference Standards. The exhaustive list for the US open data portal has not been identified.

The recommended use of controlled vocabularies shows the metadata field for each ODP that the use of controlled vocabularies is highly recommended but not mandatory, while the latter is shown in the line after. The minimum set of metadata fields required to describe a given dataset in the ODPs, and the minimum set of metadata fields required to fulfil the mandatory conditions for each ODP simultaneously are shown also in Table 1. Seventeen (17) metadata fields are required to describe a dataset that contains all the mandatory information required by all three portals. The minimum set of metadata fields connected is an attempt to create a set of metadata elements which is (given the current data) fully interoperable among the various ODPs, indicating that the same name and structure are followed, along with the same standardised value format or use of controlled vocabulary (codelist). This was observed for only the two fields “dct:issued” and “dct:modified” which use exactly the same reserved structure (ISO 8601 Date and Time) in all ODPs, while the last three “dct:language”, “dcat:contactPoint” and “dct:mediaType” are aligned for 2 out of 3 portals but not for all 3. Generally, the mandatory and non-mandatory fields distribution among the portals can be seen in Figure 2. Finally, on the metadata scale of the Metadata Management Maturity Model (ISA), all three portals belong to the highest level (Level 5: Linked Open Metadata) taking into account that they follow linked data principles, the reuse of known vocabularies and schemas (e.g., RDF), allowing for better interlinked information. This is not surprising since in this case 3 of the currently biggest ODPs are under analysis, however, this might not be the case when smaller ODPs are considered and analysed.

Figure 2: The distribution among mandatory and non-mandatory fields in the ODPs metadata schemas

Proceeding to the second part of the analysis methodology (which also helped determine various aspects of Table 1), the mapping of dcat:Dataset and dcat:Distribution classes (based on DCAT 2.0 and DCAT-AP 3.0) to the respective classes and values of the analysed ODPs is shown in Table 2.

The mapping performed provides a number of observations regarding the current descriptive metadata fields of the three ODPs. The alignment between the dcat schema and the respective schemas of the other portals is evident, however, a noticeable variety in the use of reserved words or lists is noticed. For instance, the field “dcat:contactPoint” recommends the use of vCard for the EU and US data portal, however, the Canadian one follows the structure of North American Profile ISO 19115. A similar situation can be seen for several other instances, such as the fields “dct:license”, “dcat:keyword” or “dct:identifier”. In addition, even when controlled vocabularies are recommended by the schema, rarely this recommendation is mandatory, which implies the value can instead be free text or custom.

Table 2: The mapping of DCAT main classes and the respective ODP schemas metadata values

dcat: Dataset/ ODPs values	European Open Data Portal	Canadian Open Data Portal	US Open Data Portal
dct:title	dct:title Literal value (e.g., string or integer), Literals containing human-readable text have an optional language tag as defined by BCP 47. ¹ Mandatory.	Term Name: “resourceTitleFrench” CKAN Term Name: “resource_name_fr” Free text. Defined by dc:title, dcterms:title. Mandatory, Conditional.	Term name: “title”. String. Human-readable name of the asset in English. Mandatory.
dct:description	dct:description May include but is not limited to: an abstract, a table of contents, a graphical representation, or a free-text account of the resource. Recommended- non-mandatory.	Term Name: “description” CKAN Term Name: “notes_en” Free text. Defined by: dc:description, dcterms:description. Other mappings: North American Profile: ISO 19115 - description, Schema.org – Thing > description, Government of Canada Recordkeeping Metadata Element Set – Description. Mandatory.	Term name: “description”. String. Human-readable. Mandatory.
dct:issued	dct:issued Literal value. Encoded using the ISO 8601 Date and Time compliant string [DATETIME] and typed using the appropriate XML Schema datatype [XMLSCHEMA11-2]. Mandatory.	Term Name: “dateReleased” CKAN Term Name: “portal_release_date” Follows the W3C Date and Time Formats, a profile of ISO 8601. Other mappings: dct:date, dcterms:date. Mandatory.	Term name: “issued”. Accepted values: ISO 8601 Date (standard for date and time data.) Non-mandatory.
dct:modified	dct:modified Literal value. Encoded using the ISO 8601 Date and Time compliant string [DATETIME] and typed using the appropriate XML Schema datatype [XMLSCHEMA11-2]. Mandatory.	Term Name: “modified” CKAN Term Name: “date_modified” Follows the W3C Date and Time Formats, a profile of ISO 8601. Other mappings: Government of Canada Recordkeeping Metadata Element Set: eventDateTime, eventType = Edited, Schema.org – Thing > CreativeWork>dateModified. Mandatory.	Term name: “modified”. Accepted values: ISO 8601 Date (standard for date and time data.) Mandatory.
dct:identifier	dct:identifier Literal value. Recommended practice is to conform to an identification system (e.g., International Standard Book Number (ISBN), Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Uniform Resource Name (URN)). Persistent identifiers should be provided as HTTP URIs. Mandatory.	Term Name: “metadataRecordIdentifier” CKAN Term Name: “id” Text. Defined by North American Profile ISO 19115. Mandatory.	Term name: “identifier”. String. Must be unique across the catalog and remain fixed. Recommended that a URI (preferably an HTTP URL) is used to provide a globally unique identifier. Identifier URLs should be designed and maintained to persist indefinitely regardless of whether the URL of the resource changes. Mandatory.

dcat:keyword	dcat:keyword Literal value. It was relaxed in DCAT 2. Non-mandatory.	Term Name: “descriptiveKeywords” CKAN Term Name: “keywords_en” Free text. Defined by North American Profile ISO 19115. Other Mappings: Schema.org – Thing > CreativeWork > keywords Mandatory.	Term name: “keyword”. Array of strings. Mandatory.
dct:language	dct:language Recommended to use a non-literal value such as a language from a controlled vocabulary (e.g., ISO 639-2 or ISO 639-3), or a literal value consisting of an IETF. Best Current Practice 47 [IETF-BCP47] language tag. Mandatory.	Term Name: “language” CKAN Term Name: “resource_language” Text. Defined by: dc:language, dcterms:language Encoded by ISO 639.2 Language Codes. ² Mandatory, Conditional.	Term name: “language”. Array of strings. Should adhere to the RFC 5646 standard. Regional subtags should only be provided when needed to distinguish one language tag from another. Non-mandatory.
dct:publisher	dct:publisher Literal value. Resources of type foaf:Agent are recommended as values. Mandatory.	Term Name: “publisherCurrentOrganizationName” CKAN Term Name: “owner_org” Text. Follows the “Publisher - Current Organization Name Codelist” encoding scheme. ³ Other mappings: Metadata Object Description Schema - <originInfo><publisher>, Schema.org - Thing > CreativeWork > publisher Mandatory.	Term name: “publisher”. Accepted value: Object. A container for a publisher object which allows one to describe an organization’s hierarchy. Mandatory.
dcat:contactPoint	dcat:contactPoint Use of vCard is recommended [VCARD-RDF]. Non-mandatory.	Term Name: “pointOfContact” CKAN Term Name: “maintainer_email” Text. Defined by North American Profile ISO 19115. Encoded by: mailto: URL. Mandatory.	Term name: “contactPoint”. Accepted value: vCard object. Should always contain both an appropriately formatted full name and email. Mandatory.
dct:accrualPeriodicity	dct:accrualPeriodicity Defined by EU Vocabularies Frequency Named Authority List ⁴ Non-mandatory.	Term Name: “maintenanceAndUpdateFrequency” CKAN Term Name: “frequency” Text. Encoded by the Maintenance and Update Frequency Codelist ⁵ (North American Profile ISO 19115) Mandatory.	Term name: “accrualPeriodicity”. Accepted value: ISO 8601 Repeating Duration (unless this is not possible because the accrual periodicity is irregular) Non-mandatory.
dcat:landingPage	dcat:landingPage Text (URL). Sub-property of: foaf:page and of Range: foaf:Document Mandatory.	Term Name: “homepageURLEngish” CKAN Term Name: “program_page_url_en” Text. Encoded by Website URL. Other mappings: Schema.org – Thing > sameAs Recommended, non-mandatory.	Term name: “landingPage”. String (URL). Non-mandatory

dcat:theme	dcat: theme The values to be used are the URIs of the concepts in the vocabulary (defined by: the Dataset Theme Vocabulary ⁶). Many SKOS fields re-used. Non-mandatory.	CKAN Term Name: "topic_category" Text, based on vocabulary encoding scheme (defined by: North American Profile ISO 19115). Mandatory.	Term name: "theme". Array of strings could include ISO Topic Categories (e.g., ISO 13250 Topic Maps standard). Non-mandatory.
dcat: Distribution/ODPs values	European Open Data Portal	Canadian Open Data Portal	US Open Data Portal
dct:title	dct:title Literal value. Mandatory.	Term Name: "resourceTitleEnglish" CKAN Term Name: "resource_name_en" Free text. Defined by: Dublin Core. Mandatory, Conditional	Term name: "title". String. Mandatory.
dct:issued	dct:issued Literal value. Encoded using the ISO 8601 Date and Time compliant string [DATETIME] and typed using the appropriate XML Schema datatype [XMLSCHEMA11-2]. Mandatory.	Term Name: "issued" CKAN Term Name: "date_published" Text. Follows the W3C Date and Time Formats, a profile of ISO 8601. Other mappings: Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) - <originInfo><dateIssued>Schema.org - Thing > CreativeWork> datePublished Mandatory.	Term name: "issued". Accepted value: ISO 8601 Date. Non-mandatory.
dct:modified	dct:modified Literal value. Encoded using the ISO 8601 Date and Time compliant string [DATETIME] and typed using the appropriate XML Schema datatype [XMLSCHEMA11-2]. Non-mandatory.	Term Name: "modified" CKAN Term Name: "date_modified" Text. Follows the W3C Date and Time Formats, a profile of ISO 8601. Other mappings: Schema.org – Thing > CreativeWork>dateModified. Mandatory.	Term name: "modified". Accepted value: ISO 8601 Date. Mandatory.
dct: license	dct: license Literal value but recommended to use URIs of well-known licenses such as Creative Commons. Non-mandatory.	Term Name: "license" CKAN Term Name: "license_id" Text. Follows the Open Government Secretariat Defined licensing list. Mandatory.	Term name: "license". String (URL). Follows the list of license-free declarations and licenses. Mandatory. ⁷
dcat: accessURL	dcat: accessURL Text (URL). If the distribution(s) are accessible only through a landing page then that URL associated with the dcat:Dataset should be duplicated as access URL. Non-mandatory.	Not found.	Term name: "accessURL". String (URL). Usually assumed that it is an HTML webpage. Non-mandatory.
dcat:downloadURL	dcat:downloadURL Text (URL). Should be used when the distribution is available directly, usually through an HTTP Get request. Recommended, non-mandatory.	Term Name: "resourceURL" CKAN Term Name: "resource_url" Text. Follows the Website URL syntax encoding scheme. Other mappings: Schema.org > Thing> CreativeWork > Dataset > distribution. Mandatory, Conditional.	Term name: "downloadURL". String (URL). Must be the direct download URL. Mandatory if the file is publicly available.

dct:format	dct:format Literal value. Recommended to use a controlled vocabulary where available (e.g., the list of Internet Media Types [MIME]) ⁸ . Mandatory.	Term Name: “format” CKAN Term Name: “resource_format” Text. Follows the Format Codelist (Treasury Board Secretariat, Information Management and Open Government Directorate). Other mappings: Schema.org – Thing > CreativeWork > fileFormat. Mandatory, Conditional.	Term name: “format”. String. A human-readable textual description of the file format of the dataset. Non-mandatory.
dct:mediaType	dct:mediaType Literal value. Defined by IANA [IANA-MEDIA-TYPES] ⁹ . Mandatory.	Term Name: “resourceType” CKAN Term Name: “resource_type” Text. Follows the Resource Type Codelist (Government of Canada Content Type Scheme, based on IMRC - dc.type Sub-Group: Government of Canada Type Scheme). ¹⁰ Mandatory, Conditional.	Term name: “mediaType”. String. Follows the machine-readable file format (IANA Media Type or MIME Type). Mandatory if the file is publicly available.
dct:byteSize	dct:byteSize Literal value. Typed as xsd:decimal (number of bytes). Recommended, non-mandatory.	Term Name: “extent” CKAN Term Name: “resource_size” Text. Follows the North American Profile: ISO 19115 – extent. Mandatory, Conditional.	Not found.

¹ <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc5646>

² http://loc.gov/standards/iso639-2/php/code_list.php

³ <https://www.tbs-sct.canada.ca/ap/fip-pcim/reg-eng.asp>

⁴ <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency>

⁵ <http://nap.geogratias.gc.ca/metadata/register/codelists-eng.html>

⁶ <https://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme>

⁷ <https://resources.data.gov/open-licenses/>

⁸ <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>

⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/#bib-iana-media-types>

¹⁰ <http://www.collectionscanada.gc.ca/webarchives/20071127031434/http://www.tbs-sct.gc.ca/im-gi/mwg-gtm/typ-typ/docs/2003/schem/scheme.asp>

5 DISCUSSION

The analysis findings allow for several conclusions regarding the metadata schemas of the examined ODPs. The adopted schemas of the three portals, at least on a descriptive/administrative metadata level that the mapping with dcat:Dataset and dcat:Distribution offers, have several points in common but also several differentiations. First of all, regardless of the similar structure and alignment with DCAT, the ODPs do not mandate the same number of metadata fields required to describe their data assets. Some portals have a significantly higher number of mandatory fields, while others have fewer. The number of mandatory fields which require the use of controlled vocabularies is relatively low in all ODPs, although there

are many metadata fields for which the use of controlled vocabularies or code lists is highly recommended (but not mandatory), allowing often for the input of free text or a loose alignment with existing reserved lists of words. From a semantic interoperability perspective, this still poses a challenge that requires further improvements, as it hampers standardisation and fully interoperable automatic operations which are key in interoperability. On the other hand, there are cases where the use of controlled vocabularies or standardised format is mandatory for all the analysed portals, but the choice of reserved list or standard followed is not the same due to geographical, country-specific, or other reasons, a practice which also does not promote a seamless exchange or discovery of data. The aspect of identifying the minimum set of

metadata fields required to satisfy the metadata conditions for all ODPs at once, would serve as a paradigm aiming to demonstrate information representation and description, not only on a ODP dataset level but also when further details of domain-specific data are to be included. In this study, the minimum set of metadata fields noted is equal to the mandatory metadata fields of the portal with the highest number of required metadata plus the remaining fields of the other portals which were not covered by the former, an approach which is not necessarily the path to follow in this regard, although it gives a first impression of the current situation regarding the choice of metadata fields to be included in each case. As far as the initial research question of this study is concerned, the ability of an imagined query which could run through all three examined ODPs and return the highest relevant dataset results for each portal remains unanswered when it comes to the current state of open data portals, however, it could be come practically feasible if a semantically common, unifying layer is designed to facilitate this process. A semantically interoperable query could be designed taking into consideration the specificities and metadata structure of the adopted schemas in order to tailor the query to its intended purpose and this could be facilitated by automated or semi-automated techniques (use of LLMs, etc.). However, the current infrastructure of open data portals, even when it comes to major ODPs such as the ones analysed in this study, requires further actions in terms of standardisation and alignment of, not only the structure but also the values of the metadata fields used in order to establish consensus among the different approaches.

6 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The present study considers three major open data portals and their metadata schemas to identify the current status in (meta)data provision. The initial selection of the three portals was based on the rationale that a comparison between portals which share a lot of common ground (in terms of data provision, metadata structure etc.) could provide us with the latest approaches in metadata schema adoption, although the inclusion of more international open data portals would provide a different perspective of the metadata quality and provision landscape leading to further lines of improvement, something which is highly recommended as a prospective direction of research for this study. Furthermore, the focus of this study was the metadata provision within the contexts of metadata quality and semantic interoperability; future directions can include specifically the study of controlled vocabularies in use by ODPs, not only on a descriptive or administrative metadata basis, but also on a structural and domain-specific basis, allowing for the elicitation of guidelines and practices to standardise knowledge domain metadata provision across the portals, enabling the process towards the identification of minimum sets of metadata descriptions applicable to various contexts, and reaching one step closer to the envisioned interoperable query paradigm. The utilisation of automated (e.g., Generative AI) or semi-automated means (combined with human expertise) for this purpose could facilitate this process, unveiling new potential in this domain and allowing for new research directions on how to practically enable the conceptualisation of a unifying semantic layer among different metadata schemas of open data portals.

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